

**IMPACT OF DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT AND PARTICIPATORY
DECISION MAKING ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE. A MEDIATING
ROLE OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE OF EDUCATIONAL SECTOR
EMPLOYEES OF HYDERABAD SINDH.**

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Abstract

This study investigates the effects of Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making on Employee Performance, with Corporate Governance acting as a mediating role among employees working in the educational sector of Hyderabad, Sindh. In today's rapidly changing organizational environment institutions are increasingly focusing on inclusive workplace practice and employee involvement to improve overall performance and long term sustainability. The primary purpose of the study is to analyze the direct and indirect influence of Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making on Employee Performance through Corporate Governance. A quantitative research design was adopted, and data were gathered through structured questionnaires from 160 employees working in educational institutions in Hyderabad, Sindh. To analyze the responses the study applied Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) which helped test reliability, validity and the relationship among the variables. The findings show that Diversity Management has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance while Participatory Decision Making has a positive but statistically insignificant direct relationship with Employee Performance. The results further show that both Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making positively and significantly influence Corporate Governance. Also Corporate Governance has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance and mediates the relationships between Diversity Management, Participatory Decision Making and Employee Performance. The study conclude that educational institutions can improve employee performance by supporting diversity, involving employees in decision making and strengthening governance practices. The findings may help managers, policymakers and researcher who want to build more inclusive and performance focused workplaces.

INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is a central force behind organizational competitiveness and long-term survival. As we face globalization, digital transformation and increasing diversity of workforce organizations are under pressure to adopt practices that enhance productivity, equality and employee wellbeing. Two such practices participatory decision making (PDM) and diversity management have been gaining growing attention in recent publication. Companies today are dealing with fast change and more competition. Because of this many of them have realize that they must rely on creativity and innovation if they want to survive and continue growing. More importantly employees are now seen as one of the main sources of this innovation. They are often the people who introduce new ideas and push organization toward new ways of doing things (Tajeddini et al., 2023). Further a well-established organization often benefits from having a workforce made up of people with different backgrounds. Employees bring in different kind of knowledge, skills and experience which not only add variety but also improve the company ability to generate new ideas. This mix of perspective and value strengthens innovation and helps organization gain and apply new knowledge more effectively. Moreover when employees are able to fully realize their potential, it makes a significant difference in how well a company can develop and make use of new products, services, systems or processes (Tajeddini et al., 2023). However if workforce diversity management is not done properly it can create misunderstandings and even fear among employees which in turn may hold back the company's ability to grow (Tajeddini et al., 2023).

Diversity management is generally concerned with solving employee issues around fairness, justice and equality especially when it comes to difference in age, gender, ethnicity or education. It also deals with practical problem at work such as employees being assigned roles that do not fit them well or being given tasks, they do not want. Studies have found that when fairness and equality are handled properly through diversity management, employees are more motivated and perform at a higher level

(Li et al., 2021). Additionally, traditional structures and business practices are gradually losing relevance as they struggle to adapt to technology driven globalization. Within organizational management, decision making serves as a clear reflection of this dynamic shift. In vertically structured organizations, centralized decision making at higher levels has traditionally been considered more effective, while in horizontally structured organizations, participatory decision making approaches that encourage active involvement of members have proven to be more efficient (Kim, 2022). As organizations continue shifting from traditional top down structures to more open and collaborative systems, giving employees a greater role in decision making is becoming a more effective way to manage and achieve results (Kim, 2022). Most organizations recognize that it is important to involve employees in different kinds of work and at different levels. Employees are not only valuable for the tasks they perform but also for the ideas and feedback they bring, which are important for building long term customer value and strengthening loyalty to the organization (Kim, 2022).

One of the ways managers encourage this is through participative decision making (PDM), which serves to enhance long term commitment and overall performance in favor of the organization. Research also show that when employees are given a say in decision they tend to perform better than competitor and feel more motivated to work toward higher productivity (Kelechi E. Ugwu et al., 2019). When employees are given chance to build up their skill and technical expertise it naturally lifts their confidence and morale. This does not just stay at the individual level it often shows up in the form of more creativity, stronger commitment and greater job satisfaction. What matters even more is when people see their ideas being acted on. At that point, they not only feel motivated but also feel recognized as they truly belong in the organization. Simply, participative decision making (PDM) helps close the gap that often exists between employees and management (Kelechi E. Ugwu et al., 2019).

Good corporate governance is also essential for the long-term success of any company. Digital transformation also plays a big role, shaping not only business sustainability and financial performance but also the governance practices of organizations. In addition, when digital technologies are applied with consideration for labor issues and when companies foster a supportive digital culture, employees are more likely to perform better and contribute positively to organizational goals (Steiner et al., 2025). For developing countries, establishing transparent practices in governance is particularly important, as inequality is still a big challenge. At the same time organization must be encouraged and made accountable for generating diversity in the workplace and providing equal opportunities. Teams work more effectively when diversity is practiced because it brings in fresh ideas and help employees feel more connected. When people feel connected they are more loyal, more committed and this usually leads to better performance (Steiner et al., 2025).

2.Literature Review

Diversity Management and Employee Performance

Former studies shows that DM positive and significant impact on the EP. Moreover, the research study of (Oljaca, 2024) aimed to assess the effect of supportive leadership, and DM on the overall employee job performance in the production area of Vietnam. Also, this study studies mediating effect of affective dedication on this association. The methodology is through the primary source which means firsthand data collection through an adopted questionnaire which was filled by 406 employees in the manufacturing industry in Vietnam. In direct reflection of results, supportive leadership and diversity management have a high enormous and high-quality effect on overall employee task performance. Correspondingly the affective commitment performs a mediating role in supportive leadership, diversity management and overall employee task performance. Khan & Javaid (2023) aimed to assess in what way diversity management (DM) impacts employee performance behaviors (EPB) and identified

mediating role of gender, religion, education, and age diversity amongst the association of diversity management and overall employee performance.

Methodology in this study is primary source of data and the questionnaire is adopted, while the respondents are 350 employees from diversified cultures, specifically from textile organizations of Pakistan. Further as per outcomes, workforce diversity management (WFM) has direct association with the overall employee performance while the mediating role of characteristics of diversity are gender, religion, age, academic history diversity, which further reflects an indirect high quality relationship amongst diversity management and overall employee performance.

Participatory Decision Making and Employee Performance

Previous research reflect that PDM has positive and significant association on employee EP. The study (Goka et al., 2024) aims to understand impact of PDM on EP in sector of health. The methodology applied is though primary source of data collection, for which an adopted questionnaire is used and the respondents are 460 nurses in Ghana. The study is explanatory research design and for the purpose of data analysis we used (PLS-SEM). The results as outcomes from this study reflect that PDM shows positive and significant association with EP in sector of health. Another research of (Kim, 2022) aim to identify the participatory decision making (PDM) lead towards employee task performance and personal growth. The methodology utilized is through primary source of data collection. The applied questionnaire adopted from the internet and responses were recorded by 385 employees working in various organizations in South Korea. The results showed that PDM has positive and significant influence on task performance (TP) of employees and their personal growth (PG). Furthermore, the study proved that the effect of PDM on TP and PG is partially mediated by factors like motivation, organizational commitment and public service motivation.

Diversity Management and Corporate Governance

The studies conducted previously reflect that DM have positive and significant association with corporate governance (CG). The study by (Shohaieb et al., 2022) supports that DM, especially in board diversity, significantly enhances effectiveness of CG and further it improves firm outcomes, as it is examined through different academic perspectives and methods. A research study examining CG and DM: Insights from a disclosure viewpoint that employed computer-aided textual analysis which is a secondary source of data collection and was applied to the yearly reports of UK FTSE non financial companies, established a core connection between board composition and transparency, verifying that "Moreover, there is a favorable association between board size, female board members and board independence and the extent of diversity management disclosure." Enhancing this viewpoint, a Conceptual Analysis aligned with Stakeholder Theory (Shanmugam et al., 2025) synthesized external evidence affirming the enhanced performance of diverse boards, indicating that "A 2020 study by McKinsey & Company found that firms with diverse boards outshine their less diverse counterparts in financial performance," and stressing its advantage for ethical governance by stating that "Studies indicate that gender diversity on corporate boards substantially influences corporate social performance."

Participatory Decision Making and Corporate Governance

As per past studies, the Participatory Decision Making (PDM) reflects impact that is positive and significant on the Corporate Governance (CG). (Del Sordo & Zattoni, 2025) aimed to examine role played by employee ownership (EO), financial participation (FP) & DM in CG. The method applied through the secondary source of data comprises of 184 published articles from reputed journals. The researcher argues that including employees in decision-making is a crucial expansion of corporate governance. They state that a company's ownership is conceived traditionally as the ownership of two interconnected rights, the

residual income right and residual control right, namely, the right to influence corporate decisions. This positions the right to decision-making not just as a management technique, but also as a fundamental governance right. The researcher further says, employee participation can be directed as "Decision Making (DM), i.e. representation of employees on the board, codetermination". Moreover, according to the author, "employee decision making may have several forms such as involvement of employees in decisions, board-level representation of employees and codetermination." Thus, the board-level employee representation and codetermination are directly identified as the structures that integrate the decision-making of employees into the company's formal corporate governance framework. (Ali et al., 2022) aims to evaluate the relationship among five principles of governance those are transparency, accountability, equity and employee participation and financial strategy implementation in Somalia. In this study, the approach employed is through primary source of data collection. Moreover, adopted questionnaire was filled by 297 number of employees who work in the finance department or for institutions of Somalia government. The researcher states, "Sense of belonging of employees and their self-realization are key to a firm's identity and loyalty as a workforce that feels involved in the process of decision making and believes its contribution and the feedback is valued, likely to commit to the realization of the overall organization's goals." This statement mirrors the fact that employees feel value when their participation in the process of decision making is valued and this lead to the creation of a sense of belonging among them.

Corporate governance and Employee Performance

The studies conducted previously shows corporate governance (CG) has positive and significant influence on employee performance (EP) of ABC's employee of Hyderabad Sindh. The study by (Sari et al., 2023) goal to study effects of good corporate governance (GCG), organizational commitment (OC) and internal controls (IC) on the performance of employees who are employed at public hospitals in the

North Sumantra in Indonesia. The research method applied is primary data collection using an adopted questionnaire to 102 hospital employees. The findings from this study reflects that GCG, OC, IC all positively and significantly influence EP in public hospitals in the North Sumantra in Indonesia. The study of (Putri & Achmad, 2024) aims to examine how the variables employee competence (EC) and good corporate governance (GCG) influence the variable employee performance (EP), while job satisfaction (JS) as mediator variable. Moreover this study is focused on the Bank BJB Bandung. The method adopted for this study is through primary source where data collection is done using an adopted questionnaire filled by 80 employees of Bank BJB Bandung. The results indicate that impact factors which are good corporate governance (GCG), employee competence (EC), & job satisfaction (JS) reflect a positive and significant influence on the employee performance (EP) at the Bank BJB Bandung, Indonesia. Furthermore, the result showed that JS play has positive as well as significant mediating role in the association among GCG and EP as well as between EC and EP.

Corporate Governance between Diversity Management and Employee Performance.

Past studies have consistently demonstrated that both Diversity Management (DM) and Corporate Governance (CG) independently enhance organizational outcomes; however, emerging evidence also suggests that CG may function as an important mediating mechanism that strengthens the positive effect of DM on employee performance. The study on diversity management disclosure by (Shohaieb et al., 2022) establishes a strong foundational link between DM and CG, demonstrating that governance structures board size, board independence and the presence of women in board significantly shape how diversity practices are communicated and embedded in organizational processes. Their findings indicate that “there is a positive relationship between the size of the board, women on board, and independence of board and the level of diversity management disclosure”. This suggests that organization with stronger governance

frameworks are more capable of translating diversity efforts into transparent, strategic and performance oriented practices. From a governance performance standpoint, (Abun et al., 2022) provide direct empirical evidence that CG significantly and positively influences on employee work outcomes in educational institutions. Their study finds that higher levels of CG operationalized through probity, strategic vision, accountability and effective monitoring are associated with improved task and contextual performance, while reducing counterproductive behaviors. According to their results, “Improved corporate governance leads to higher individual work performance and it likewise minimize counterproductive behavior among employees.”. This reinforces the argument that CG serves as an internal control system that guides behavioral norms, clarifies expectations and enhances employee motivation key channels through which diversity initiatives also aim to improve performance. Furthermore research linking board diversity to governance quality offers additional support for CG mediating role.

Corporate Governance Between Participatory Decision Making and Employee Performance.

The theoretical background derived from the literature leads to the hypothesis that corporate governance mediates the relationship between participatory decision making and employee performance. The research by (Del Sordo & Zattoni, 2025) aims to analyze the role of Employee Ownership (EO), Financial Participation (FP) and DM in CG. The methodology in the research is through the secondary source of data which includes 184 published articles in upright journals. In this research the researcher states that ownership of company is perceived as ownership of two rights that are interrelated, first is the residual income right which is referred as the right to receive the net income of corporation and the other is the residual control right which is being referred as the right to impact corporate decisions. This means that enabling employee participation in decisions is more than just a management practice as it is a significant part of how the corporation is run and controlled at a fundamental level. The researcher states in their article, their analysis of 50 years of study

incorporates and compares evidence and theory from three independent yet entwined domains namely, employee ownership (EO), financial participation (FP) and decision making (DM), establishes the profound effect this governance structure has on employees. The article by Del (Del Sordo & Zattoni, 2025) further states, a useful classification discriminates these plans based on the degree of allocation of two rights, such as the residual return rights and the residual control rights. Now, amongst two of these extremes, they choose to position plans emphasizing employee participation either to financial results or to decision making, i.e. employee board representation,

3. Conceptual Model

This study employs a quantitative research approach. In the present study, this approach was adopted to examine the relationships among key variables, including Diversity Management (DM), Participatory Decision Making (PDM), and Employee Performance, with Corporate Governance serving as a mediating factor. For this study, an explanatory research design was adopted and in this type of design, data is gathered using a structured questionnaire survey. Moreover, the data will be collected from the educational sector of Hyderabad Sindh.

The data source for this study is primary. In this study, the population consists of associate level

codetermination. The clearly categorizes form of Participatory decision making (PDM) which is being referred as board representation as indicator of “residual control right”, that is, a core governance right.

Employees in the educational sector of Hyderabad Sindh. We used purposive sampling, also known as the non-probability sampling method, for purpose of collecting data from employees. This questionnaire is based on the 5-Likert Scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree and analyze data through PLS SEM. According to the Rule of Thumb, we have a total number of questions which is 16 and 4 questions per variable across 4 variables. Thus, we used 160 respondents.

5. Results & Discussion.

Reliability Analysis.

Table 1. Internal Consistency and Reliability.

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	(rho_a)	(rho_c)	(AVE)
Corporate Governance	0.848	0.850	0.898	0.687
Diversity Management	0.716	0.716	0.821	0.534
Employee Performance	0.815	0.829	0.878	0.643
Participatory Decision Making	0.862	0.870	0.906	0.707

The evaluation of PLS SEM starts with the assessment of the measurement model. This stage include examining internal consistency reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity. Internal consistency reliability was assessed through Cronbach alpha, rho_a and rho_c (Hair et al., 2019). The value of Cronbach alpha ranged from 0.716 to 0.862 while rho_a values ranged from 0.716 to 0.870 all exceeding the recommended threshold of

0.70 and demonstrating acceptable reliability. In addition rho_c values which ranged between 0.821 and 0.906 further supported strong internal consistency. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values were all higher than the minimum threshold of 0.50 confirming convergent validity. These finding indicate that the measurement model is reliable and valid.

Table 2. Discriminant Validity.

Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT)	CG	DM	EP	PDM
CG				
DM	0.854			
EP	0.710	0.743		
PDM	0.822	0.814	0.595	

Discriminant validity confirm that each latent variable is sepearate from the others in the model. In this study, the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio was used to analyze discriminant validity, as recommended by Hair et al. and Henseler et al. According to these guidelines, discriminant validity is determined when the

HTMT values are below 0.85 or 0.90. As shown in Table 6, none of the HTMT values exceed the benchmark of 0.90, highlighting that the constructs in the model are adequately distinct from each other.

Table 3. Hypothesis Testing

Path Coefficient	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Value
CG → EP	0.335	0.342	0.091	3.669	0.000
DM → CG	0.381	0.373	0.075	5.069	0.000
DM → EP	0.344	0.327	0.102	3.378	0.001
PDM → CG	0.463	0.476	0.083	5.583	0.000
PDM → EP	0.047	0.058	0.101	0.460	0.646
DM → CG → EP	0.127	0.128	0.045	2.854	0.005
PDM → CG → EP	0.155	0.162	0.050	3.119	0.002

Table 3 indicates that the path coefficient for the relationship between CG and EP is 0.335 ($p = 0.000$), showing a highly significant positive association at the 5% significance level between Corporate Governance and Employee Performance. Similarly, DM and CG exhibit a positive path coefficient of 0.381 ($p = 0.000$) which is also highly significant confirming that Diversity Management positively affects Corporate Governance. The connection between DM and EP is likewise statistically significant with a path coefficient of 0.344 ($p = 0.001$) showing that Diversity Management has a strong positive influence on Employee Performance. In the same way the relationship between PDM and CG is highly significant as shown in path coefficient of 0.463 ($p = 0.000$) indicating a strong positive effect. The result further reveal that PDM exert a significant positive influence on Corporate Governance (CG) ($\beta = 0.463$, $p = 0.000$) highlighting the strength of this relationship. In contrast the direct association between PDM and Employee Performance (EP) is statistically insignificant ($\beta = 0.047$, $p = 0.646$) suggesting that PDM does not directly impact employee performance. For the indirect effects DM demonstrates a significant influence on EP through CG with a path coefficient of 0.127 ($p = 0.005$). This finding implies that Corporate Governance act as an important mediating variable in the relationship between Diversity Management and Employee Performance. Likewise, PDM also produces a significant indirect effect on EP through CG ($\beta = 0.155$, $p = 0.002$). These findings show that although PDM does not directly improve Employee Performance it contributes positively through the mediating effect of Corporate Governance.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This study is based on Impact of Diversity Management (DM), Participatory Decision Making (PDM) on Employee Performance (EP), where Corporate Governance (CG) playing its role as mediator towards the employees of educational sector of Hyderabad Sindh. The results that came from hypothesis testing confirm that DM shows positive and significant

influence on EP whereas PDM reflects positive but insignificant yet direct effect on EP. DM and PDM are found to have positive and significant impact on CG and CG reflect positive and significant impact on EP. Additionally, both indirect effects of DM and PDM on EP through CG are positive and significant.

Implications

The theoretical perspective is improvised by this study which concluded that the Impact of DM and PDM on EP with CG playing its role as a mediator towards the employees in the educational sector in Hyderabad Sindh. Moreover, this theory also added value to the theoretical contribution, as this research concludes that DM and PDM confirms to have positive and significant impact on EP & CG significantly mediates this association. DM and PDM acts as a crucial function in strengthening EP which further leads towards the success of the organization. The study examines the impact of DM and PDM on EP, with CG as a mediator toward employees in the educational sector in Hyderabad, Sindh. Moreover, this study assists organizations that are willing to go for innovation and advancement, where managers and employees who are working on Diversity and Participatory Decision Making practices that overall influence Employee Performance through strengthening Corporate Governance will benefit from the findings.

Recommendation on Results

The recommendation on results, as per results, the impact of Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making on Employee Performance, a mediating role of Corporate Governance. The results confirms that DM on EP ($B = 0.344$, $p < 0.05$), PDM on PDM ($B = 0.047$, $p > 0.05$), DM on CG ($B = 0.381$, $p < 0.05$), PDM on CG ($B = 0.463$, $p < 0.05$), CG on EP ($B = 0.335$, $p < 0.05$), indirect effect of DM on EP through CG ($B = 0.127$, $p < 0.05$), and the indirect effect of PDM on EP through CG ($B = 0.155$, $p < 0.05$). This reflects that except Participatory Decision Making on Employee Performance, all other direct & indirect relationships between variables have a positive and significant impact. Moreover, this

shows that, to improve Employee Performance, there should be more attention paid to Diversity Management and Corporate Governance as their beta has a positive relationship, which reflects higher Diversity Management and Corporate Governance will lead to higher Employee Performance. In addition, to improve Corporate Governance, there should be more focus on Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making as their beta has a positive relationship, which reflects that higher Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making will lead to higher Corporate Governance. Moreover, the significant indirect effects confirm that Corporate Governance plays a mediating role through Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making, in addition to improving Employee Performance indirectly through strengthening Corporate Governance.

Recommendation for Future Research

Firstly, this research is based on the impact of Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making on Employee Performance with Corporate Governance as a mediator towards the employees in the educational sector in Hyderabad, Sindh. Our aim was to identify more factors using more variables but due to time constraints we selected two independent variables namely Diversity Management and Participatory Decision Making and one mediator named Corporate Governance to examine the impact of Employee performance which is a dependent variable in this study. In the future, researchers can take on more variables to study a more detailed perspective. Secondly, our study is limited to 160 respondents due to shortage of time, so in future, the researchers can take on a larger sample size for better results. This study is limited to Hyderabad, Sindh and focused on the Educational sector as it was practically not possible to conduct a survey of larger audience geographically with respect to time we had. So, future researchers can incorporate more geographic locations and expand their research to other cities and can incorporate other sectors, i.e. banking, healthcare, etc., which will strengthen the validity of their findings.

REFERENCES

- Abun, D., Ranay, F. B., Magallanes, T., & Encarnacion, M. J. (2022). The effect of corporate governance on the individual work performance of employees: The case of private higher education. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147-4478), 11(3), 82–98. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v11i3.1763>
- Ali, A. A., Senaji, T. A., & Awino, D. O. (2022). Governance and Strategy Implementation in the Federal Government of Somalia. *Journal of Strategic Management*, 2(1), 35–44. <https://doi.org/10.70619/vol2iss1pp35-44>
- Del Sordo, E., & Zattoni, A. (2025). The Role of Employee Ownership, Financial Participation, and Decision-Making in Corporate Governance: A Multilevel Review and Research Agenda. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 33(3), 529–549. <https://doi.org/10.1111/corg.12614>
- Goka, K., Agormedah, E., Achina, S., & Moses, S. (2024). How Dimensions of Participatory Decision Making Influence Employee Performance in the Health Sector: A Developing Economy Perspective. *Journal of Chinese Human Resources Management*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.47297/wspchrmWS P2040-800506.20241501>
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- Kelechi E. Ugwu, Lazarus I. Okoroji, & Ebere Oluchi Chukwu. (2019). Participative Decision Making and Employee Performance in the Hospitality Industry: A Study of Selected Hotels in Owerri Metropolis, Imo State. *Management Studies and Economic Systems*, 4(1), 57–70. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0053651>

- Khan, K., & Javaid, Z. K. (2023). Analyzing Employee Performance through Workforce Diversity Management: Role of Workforce Diversity Characteristics. *Foundation University Journal of Business & Economics*, 8(2), 85-101. <https://doi.org/10.33897/fujbe.v8i2.811>
- Kim, J. S. (2022). An Empirical Analysis of the Relationships among Participatory Decision Making and Employees' Task Performance and Personal Growth. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12392. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912392>
- Li, Z., Oljaca, M., Firdousi, S. F., & Akram, U. (2021). Managing Diversity in the Chinese Organizational Context: The Impact of Workforce Diversity Management on Employee Job Performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 733429. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.733429>
- Oljaca, M. (2024). Enhancing Employee Job Performance Through Supportive Leadership, Diversity Management, and Employee Commitment: The Mediating Role of Affective Commitment. *Journal of International Business Research and Marketing*, 8(3), 12-26. <https://doi.org/10.18775/jibrm.1849-8558.2015.83.3002>
- Putri, E. K. S., & Achmad, N. (2024). Empowering Excellence: The Impact of Corporate Governance and Employee Competence on Performance. *Jurnal Orientasi Bisnis Dan Entrepreneurship (JOBS)*, 5(2), 108-121. <https://doi.org/10.33476/jobs.v5i2.4701>
- Sari, M., Dahrani, & Aprilyani Sagala, N. (2023). Determinants of employee performance at public hospitals in Indonesia: Examining the moderating role of organizational culture. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 22(1), 57-68. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.22\(1\).2024.06](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.22(1).2024.06)
- Shanmugam, J. K., Said, R. H., Jailuddin, N. A., & Karim, Z. A. (2025). Conceptual Analysis of Board Diversity and Corporate Governance: A Catalyst for Sustainable Growth and Ethical Leadership.
- Shohaieb, D., Elmarzouky, M., & Albitar, K. (2022). Corporate governance and diversity management: Evidence from a disclosure perspective. *International Journal of Accounting & Information Management*, 30(4), 502-525. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJAIM-03-2022-0058>
- Steiner, A. A., Lerman, L. V., Kai, D. A., & Benitez, G. B. (2025). Digital corporate governance at diversity, equity, and inclusion in operations and supply chain management: A mixed-method approach. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 109724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2025.109724>
- Tajeddini, K., Budur, T., Gamage, T. C., Demir, A., Zaim, H., & Topal, R. (2023). Impact of diversity management on innovative work behavior: Mediating role of human resource management and affective commitment. *Journal of Management Development*, 42(1), 29-53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD-06-2022-0154>